

Software Package: Causal Temporal Reasoning for Markov Decision Processes

February 5, 2024

1 Introduction

This document provides instructions for running the case studies for the SPIN 2024 submission.

2 Preparation

2.1 Installing Docker

To install Docker, please refer to the official Docker documentation or your system's package manager instructions.

2.2 Building the Docker Image

To build the Docker image, navigate to the directory containing your 'Dockerfile' and run the following command:

Listing 1: Building the Docker Container

```
docker build --pull --rm -f "Dockerfile" -t artifact-pcftl:latest "."
```

This command will:

- Pull the latest base image if it's not present locally.
- Remove intermediate containers after a successful build.
- Use the 'Dockerfile' present in the current directory.
- Tag the built image as 'artifact-pcftl:latest'.

2.3 Running the Docker Container

After building the image, you can run a container using the following command:

Listing 2: Running the Docker Container

```
docker run -it artifact-pcftl:latest /bin/bash
```

This will start a container from the ‘artifact-pcftl:latest’ image and open an interactive bash shell inside it.

3 Results of the paper

3.1 Light Switch example

The results of the light switch example can be produced by running the following code:

```
cd /usr/src/1-LightSwitch
python3 main.py
```

The figures are saved in the Figs folder.

3.2 Gridworld example

The results of the gridworld example can be reproduced by running the following commands:

```
cd /usr/src/2-GridworldExample
python3 main.py
```

Figures will be saved in the results folder.

3.3 MiniGrid example

The training for different environments can be done using the code provided in the torchac repository. To train the PPO agent and the under-trained agent, use the following code for the DoorKey environment:

Listing 3: MiniGrid Case Study Training Commands

```
python3 -m scripts.train --algo ppo --env MiniGrid-DoorKey-6x6-v0
--model DoorKeySixRANDOM --save-interval 1 --frames 200
python3 -m scripts.train --algo ppo --env MiniGrid-DoorKey-6x6-v0
--model DoorKeySixPPO --save-interval 10 --frames 1000000
```

To run that for all of the environments, you can execute:

Listing 4: MiniGrid Case Study Training Commands for all environments

```
cd 3-MiniGrid-Code
./main_training.sh
```

In the interest of time, all the data regarding the training is in the Docker container, and the training is not necessary. For model-checking, one just needs to run the following code for each environment:

Listing 5: MiniGrid Case Study Model-checking Commands

```
python3 -m check_the_code --env MiniGrid-DoorKey-6x6-v0
--model_cf DoorKeySixRANDOM --model DoorKeySixPPO --episodes 50
python3 -m check_the_code --env MiniGrid-DoorKey-6x6-v0
--model_cf DoorKeySixRANDOM --model DoorKeySixPPO --episodes 50 --t_cf 10
```

To run that for all of the environments, you can execute:

Listing 6: MiniGrid Case Study Model-checking Commands for all environments

```
cd 3-MiniGrid-Code
./main_model_checking.sh
```

4 Resources

The case studies were executed on a Dell Inc. Precision 7670 laptop. The specifications of this machine include 32.0 GiB RAM, a 12th Gen Intel® Core™ i7-12850HX with 24 cores, and a dual graphics setup consisting of NVIDIA Corporation and Mesa Intel® UHD Graphics (ADL-S GT1).

The Lightswitch example completes in under a minute, while the Gridworld example takes less than an hour. For the MiniGrid example, both the learning and model checking for each case study finish in under 8 hours. To expedite the process, the PPO and random agent models are incorporated into the repeatability submission.